

THE EFFECT OF USING LEARNING MEDIA ON STUDENTS' MASTERY LEARNING

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Abstract.

This study aimed to determine the effect of using learning media to achieve students' mastery learning in every level of education from elementary, junior, and senior high school. This study used meta-analysis, which is a study of some research results focusing on similar problems. The unit of analysis in this study was written documents about research on the use of learning media, such as journal articles and research reports. These scientific documents were selected purposively in agreement with research themes about using learning media to achieve students' completeness in learning. Quantitative analysis of the data was used, with a t-test to see how big the effect of using learning media to the students' classical completeness in elementary, junior and senior high school. The results showed that the use of learning media in the learning process was very influential on students' learning completeness in a classical, where the results obtained by the analyze t-count > t-table. This means that there was a significant effect of using learning media to students' mastery learning in classical. The result of data analysis of elementary level obtained t-count = 17,765 > t-table = 1,990 ($\alpha = 5\%$), junior high school level obtained t-count = 11,284 > t-table = 2.011 ($\alpha = 5\%$), senior/vocational high school level obtained t-count = 7,641 > t-table = 1,990 ($\alpha = 5\%$).

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1. Introduction

One of the educational standards that are very influential on education implementation is an availability of adequate educational facilities and infrastructure in the learning process at every level of education. Each level of education provides facilities and infrastructure to fulfill educational needs in accordance with the growth and development of physical potential, intellectual intelligence, social, emotional, and psychological learners. Provision of educational facilities and infrastructure aims to achieve learning objectives for learners. The main components of educational facilities and infrastructure consist of land, buildings, equipment, and school furniture. Education facilities generally include all facilities that are directly intended to support the educational process, such as buildings, classrooms, learning media, tables, chairs and others. While educational infrastructure indirectly supports the implementation of educational processes, such as yard, school park, and access to school. In order for all education facilities and infrastructure to make a useful contribution to the implementation of education at every level of education, it must be managed effectively and efficiently. Facilities and infrastructure are very important in supporting the learning process in schools for teachers and learners. For students will be more helpful with the support of facilities and infrastructure in learning. Not all learners have a good level of intelligence so that the use of learning infrastructure will help learners, especially those who have weaknesses in following the learning activities. Therefore, teachers might be

creative and innovative in utilizing educational facilities in the learning process, so that learning objectives would be achieved from the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects of learners.

Learning media is one of the educational facilities that should be utilized by teachers in learning. The purpose of using learning media is a tool for teachers to facilitate learners in understanding the subject matter, so that students will be attractive and interactive in learning. Gerlach & Ely (1971) in Arsyad (2008: 3), said that the media, when understood in broad outline, are human, material, or events that build conditions that enable students to acquire knowledge, skills, or attitudes. In this sense, teachers, textbooks, learning tools, and school environments are the media.

According to Asyhar (2011: 8), learning media is anything that able to deliver or distribute messages from a source in a planned manner, resulting in a conducive learning environment where the recipient can perform the learning process efficiently and effectively. According to Aqib (2016: 50), learning media is everything that can be used to deliver the message and stimulate the learning process of the learner. Meanwhile, according to Djamarah and Zain (2010: 121), the media is a tool that can be used as a message distributor to achieve the purpose of teaching.

Hamalik (1986) in Arsyad (2008: 15) argues that using learning media in teaching and learning ability to generate new desires and interests, generate motivation and stimulation of learning activities, and even bring psychological influences on students. Levie & Lentz (1982) in Arsyad (2008: 16) recalled four functions of instructional media, especially visual media, there are (1) Attention function, visual media is the core, that is attracting and directing the attention of students to concentrate on the content of the lesson related to visual meanings displayed or accompanying text subject matter. Thus, the possibility to obtain and remember the content of the lessons is greater; (2) Affective function, visual media can be seen from the student's enjoyment level when learning (or reading) the pictorial text. Visual images or symbols can inspire students' emotions and attitudes; (3) Cognitive function, visual media facilitate the achievement of goal to comprehend and remember information or message contained in picture; (4) Compensatory function, learning media in the form of visual media helps weak students in reading to organize information in text and recall it. In other words, learning media serves to accommodate weak students and slowly accepts and understands the content of the lessons presented in text or presented verbally.

Based on the development of technology according to Arsyad (2008: 29), the learning media are grouped into four groups, there are (1) printed media, (2) audio-visual media, (3) media based on computer technology, and (4) print and computer technology. The grouping of media by Seels & Glasgow (1990) in Arsyad (2008: 33) consists of two types of media: (1) Traditional media, projected visual silhouette (non-transparent projection, overhead projection, slides, filmstrips), non-projected visuals (images, posters, photographs, charts, graphics, diagrams, exhibitions), audio (recording plates, cassette tapes, reels, cartridges), multimedia, projected dynamic visuals (film, television, video), print (textbooks, modules, workbooks, scientific magazines, hand-outs), games (puzzles, simulations, board games), realia (model, specimen, manipulative like a map, doll); (2) Advanced Media Technology, telecommunication-based media (teleconferencing, distance learning), microprocessor-based media (computer-assisted instruction, computer games, intelligent tutoring system, interactive, hypermedia, video compact disc).

Effective learning requires good planning. The media to be used in the learning process also requires good planning. Some of the criteria for choosing instructional media according to Arsyad (2008: 75) are as follows: (1) in accordance with the objectives to be achieved, the media are selected based on generally defined instructional objectives referring to one or a combination of two or three from cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects; (2)

appropriate to support the content of the lesson in the nature of facts, concepts, principles, or generalizations, in order to help the learning process effectively, the media might be aligned and in accordance with the needs of learning tasks and mental abilities of students; (3) practical, flexible and persistent, the selected medium should be used anywhere and anytime with the equipment available in the vicinity, and easily transported and carried everywhere; (4) the teacher should be able to use it in the learning process; (5) media selection based on target groupings; (6) media technical quality.

Selection of instructional media must be right on target in accordance with the needs and allow for good interaction between learners with media used so that learning information would be absorbed by learners optimally, and will change the behavior of learners. The use of the learning media from the cognitive domain is expected to improve the learning outcomes of learners in relation to the minimal achievement of the mastery learning that should be obtained by learners.

One of the teachers' authority in the learning process is to provide an assessment to the learners. Three aspects that will be assessed by teachers of learners are cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. According to Sudijono (2001), the assessment for the cognitive and psychomotor aspects can be a number that is at least 75, while for the affective aspect of the letters A, B, C, and D is very good, good, sufficient and lacking statements. According to Amirano and Daryanto (2016), mastery learning is the lowest criterion to declare the learner to complete the learning outcomes. If learners are able to get the score above the mastery learning then it is considered that the learners have completed or mastered the competencies were learned.

Although the scores of these three aspects have been established nationally, that is, the minimum mastery of learners is 75, but the school is still authorized to determine the Minimum Completion to students' mastery learning according to the condition of each school. According to Daryanto and Dwicahyono (2014: 147), the mastery learning is established by a school at the beginning of the school year by taking into account, (a) the intake or average ability of the learners; (b) the complexity of identifying indicators as markers of achieving basic competencies; (c) power support capability, ie oriented to learning resources.

Using media in the learning process in each level of education is expected to help learners achieve the minimal mastery learning determined from each lesson. In this article, researcher will see the effect of learning media on the completeness of student learning from elementary school, junior high school and senior/vocational high school using meta-analysis design.

2. Materials and Methods

The research used in explanation research with meta-analysis design. According to Sudaryono (2017), Explanation research is a study that explains the relationship between one variable with another variable by using statistical analysis. This research used a meta-analysis design. Meta-analysis is defined as an analysis of the analysis. Meta-analysis is a secondary analysis after other researchers have done their own analyses, allowing the meta-analyzer to go beyond what had been accomplished in the past. Steps of meta-analysis are formulating a problem for meta-analysis, searching literature, evaluating literature, statistically analyzing effect size and reporting the result(s) of the meta-analysis. To perform a meta-analysis, the researcher computes an effect size and variance for each study and then computes a weighted mean of these effect sizes. Effect size is a measure of strength in meta-analysis. According to Rothstein et al (2009: 3), the effect size, which reflects the magnitude of the treatment effector is the unit of currency in a meta-analysis.

Meta-analysis in this study examined the results of similar research. Instruments used in this study were humans and their learning. After the focus of the research was clear, it was

developed into a simple research instrument, which was expected to complete the data for comparison with previously found data.

Data collection employed documentation techniques. The population/sample in this research was all written documents about the influence of using learning media on students' mastery learning. The written documents were journal articles. Data or information obtained from each sample was determined based on its compatibility with the theme of this research.

Analysis of the data used is quantitative data analysis and qualitative data. To analyze the quantitative data the researcher used a t-test to measure the effect of learning media on student learning classical completeness, whereas for qualitative data the researcher used the data from the narrative study results section towards the results of the present study.

3. Results and Discussion

The research on the effect of using learning media to the students' learning completeness in elementary, junior and senior or vocational high school is obtained to be analyzed was collected from 105 research articles. The purpose of the previous studies that became the sample of the present study were mainly to investigate the effect of using learning media on students' mastery learning in elementary, junior and senior or vocational high school and to find out how big the effect of using learning media in different education level by using t-test.

Table 1. Research Population/Sample

Populasi/sampel study	Frequency
Elementary School	47
Junior High School	24
Senior/Vocational High School	34
Total	105

The result of the previous studies from 105 articles was collected to analyze showed that there was a significant effect of using learning media on students' learning outcomes from first learning cycle before using instructional media and the second cycle after using instructional media.

Table 2. Previous Research Articles analyzed about The Effect of Using Learning Media on students' mastery learning in the elementary school level.

No of Article	Learning Outcomes (%)		No of Article	Learning Outcomes (%)	
	Mastery Learning cycle I	Mastery Learning cycle II		Mastery Learning cycle I	Mastery Learning cycle II
1	60	90	25	20.08	95.80
2	55	100	26	80	93
3	73.30	86.70	27	60	97
4	66.66	93.33	28	66.70	85.20
5	40	100	29	62.50	100
6	57	93	30	34.61	76.92
7	65	100	31	71.40	90.50
8	36.36	100	32	22.20	100
9	52.63	84.21	33	45	85
10	62.50	87.50	34	47.05	82.35
11	52	80	34	66	77.70
12	65	85	36	38.89	83.33
13	41.60	95.80	37	51.61	93.55
14	60	90	38	56.67	89.33

15	55	90	39	67	87
16	13	91	40	35	73.75
17	77.50	87.50	41	63	82
18	78.26	95.65	42	50	81.25
19	60	100	43	64	100
20	54.29	85.71	44	44.44	74.44
21	55	95	45	50	100
22	45	90	46	61.54	80.76
23	69.23	98.80	47	66.67	91.67
24	62.07	93.10			

Table 3. Previous Research Articles analyzed about The Effect of Using Learning Media on students' mastery learning in the junior high school level.

No of Article	Learning Outcomes (%)		No of Article	Learning Outcomes (%)	
	Mastery Learning cycle I	Mastery Learning cycle II		Mastery Learning cycle I	Mastery Learning cycle II
1	60	90	13	70	100
2	52.17	86.96	14	47.37	94.74
3	50	88.46	15	60.71	100
4	46.30	65.40	16	74.20	100
5	65	85	17	24.99	89.28
6	69	86	18	36.70	77.80
7	50	97.05	19	19.40	96.80
8	50	90	20	72	96
9	60	80	21	50	87.09
10	60	90	22	51.43	94.29
11	50	90	23	52	86
12	50	90	24	25	91.66

Table 4. Previous Research Articles analyzed about The Effect of Using Learning Media on students' mastery learning in the Senior or Vocational High School level.

No of Article	Learning Outcomes (%)		No of Article	Learning Outcomes (%)	
	Mastery Learning cycle I	Mastery Learning cycle II		Mastery Learning cycle I	Mastery Learning cycle II
1	28	100	18	25.71	52.29
2	76.67	83.33	19	59	92.50
3	58	87	20	46.88	75
4	73	90	21	87.10	100
5	83.33	90	22	33	76
6	70	92.86	23	70.37	88.89
7	63.64	86.36	24	79.30	100
8	63.64	72.73	25	78.58	85.71
9	30.56	91.67	26	72.50	87.18
10	47.83	82.61	27	50	90
11	68.75	90.63	28	60	90
12	52.50	67.50	29	50	90

13	30	94.59	30	60	90
14	81	94	31	89.47	100
15	37.50	87.50	32	60.61	85.29
16	51.61	77.42	33	43.75	84.38
17	55.17	86.21	34	89.47	100

From the results by using the statistical analysis with a t-test showed a significant effect of using learning media to the students' classical completeness in learning. The effect of using learning media in each level of education shows the difference level of significance among elementary, junior, and senior or vocational high school students. The following data showed the analysis of the present studies about the effect of using learning media to students' mastery learning in each level of education with statistical analysis.

Table 5. Present Analysis Results of The Effect of Using Learning Media to Students' Mastery Learning in Classical.

Education Level	Frequency of Previous Articles	Analysis Result with t-test	
		t-count	t-table
Elementary School	47	17.765	$\alpha=5\% = 1.990$ $\alpha=1\% = 2.638$
Junior High School	24	11.284	$\alpha=5\% = 2.011$ $\alpha=1\% = 2.682$
Senior/Vocational High School	34	7.641	$\alpha=5\% = 1.990$ $\alpha=1\% = 2.638$

Based on the statistical analysis with t-test showed that the results of $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ for each level of education, its meaning there were significant effect of using learning media to students' classical completeness in learning. There were different level of significance from each level of education, where using learning media is very significant effect on completeness on students' mastery learning in elementary education level compared with junior and senior or vocational high school students. The statistical analysis in elementary obtained $t\text{-count} 17.765 > t\text{-table} 1.990$ with $\alpha = 5\%$, in junior high school obtained $t\text{-count} 11.284 > t\text{-table} 2.011$ with $\alpha = 5\%$, and in senior or vocational high school obtained $7.642 > t\text{-table} 1.990$ with $\alpha = 5\%$.

Using learning media has more significant effect on elementary education level because according to Kurniasih & Sani (2017), there are some of the characteristics of elementary school students: (1) playful pleasure, this characteristic requires elementary school teachers to carry out educational activities that are charged games especially for low grade and teachers are expected to design learning models that allow for the element of the game inside it; (2) elementary school children enjoy feeling or performing or demonstrating something directly, thus the teacher should design a learning model that enables the child to be directly involved in the learning process such as using learning media.

According to Jean Piaget in Jumaris (2013: 151), in the theory of cognitive development of primary school children aged 7-12 years will present themselves in the form of the ability to think logically and rationally to the events that appear concretely. So that using learning media such as models, realia, dioramas, and photos are a very supportive level of cognitive development of students in learning. whereas according to Piaget, middle and high school children who have age above 12 years in this phase of cognitive development present themselves in the form of the ability to think abstractly, in terms of their ability to hypothesize

and predict things that will happen. therefore, on children with age above 12 years can use learning media such as audio, video, media presentations, graphics, images, and multimedia in instructional process.

4. Conclusion

The use of learning media is very influential on the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects of students in learning. Learning media can arouse students' interest to be more attractive in learning. Learning media is very helpful for elementary students to understand the subject matter that is taught because it is presented visually through models, realia, dioramas, pictures, and games. As a result, elementary students can get the value of learning above the minimum learning mastery standard specified.

Using learning media also has a significant effect to junior high school and senior or vocational high school students to achieve the learning outcomes. Therefore, using learning media such as audio, video, media presentations, graphics, images, and multimedia can foster students' motivation to learn and improve student learning outcomes both individually and in classically.

From the 105 previous articles was collected to analyze, the studies were showed significant effect of using learning media to achieve students' mastery learning in classical. So, it can be concluded that using the learning media can help students to build their motivation and increase their understanding in learning.

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